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EPH 530E 01-Design Thinking Project

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MEMO/GRANT: IMPROVING CHILDHOOD VACCINATION RATES IN DRC

Identification of the Reader:

This memo/grant aims to raise awareness and improve childhood vaccination rates in the Democratic of the Congo. It mainly targets hesitant parents and public health authorities by engaging them in meaningful discussions and collaboration to overcome the challenges hindering the low childhood vaccination rates. ([Declining Vaccination Rates in the Democratic Republic of the Congo Could Lead to Resurgence in Deadly Diseases, n.d.-c](#))

Involving public health authorities as readers, the message will align strategies with their expertise, gain support, and foster collaboration to overcome all barriers to vaccination.

Parents are reluctant to vaccinate due to a lack of education, misinformation, cultural beliefs, and fear of contacting vaccination workers because of COVID-19. Empathizing with parents' perspectives and providing the proper education would build trust, foster an open dialogue and improve vaccination rates among their vulnerable children. ([Government of the Democratic Republic of Congo Doubles Its Funding for Vaccines, n.d.-b](#))

Public health authorities will design and implement the most effective strategies to strengthen the Congolese healthcare system to improve vaccination rates and overall childhood well-being by involving these parents as critical stakeholders. ([Olson et al., 2020b](#))

Description of the challenge

The DRC's low childhood immunization rate threatens the public health system. Vaccine-preventable diseases may cause significant health problems, impairments, and high mortality in unvaccinated children. Lack of faith in a broken healthcare system, cultural beliefs, vaccination misinformation, and fear of long-term adverse effects may contribute to parental vaccine hesitancy.

One of the most recent surveys, Global Citizen, found that only 35% of Congolese children are vaccinated before their first birthday. This is far lower than the predicted worldwide average making the DRC far from the only country facing setbacks in its vaccination efforts. ([Wiggins, 2020](#))

Over the last years, all recommended early childhood vaccines (hepatitis B, diphtheria, tetanus, whooping cough, and Hib) have dropped 8–10%. IPV coverage has dropped 8.4%, and OPV 3 5.4%. Chickenpox, measles, yellow fever, pneumococcal disease, and rotavirus immunizations have dropped from 4.5 to 1.5 percent. ([Declining Vaccination Rates in the Democratic Republic of the Congo Could Lead to Resurgence in Deadly Diseases, n.d.-b](#))

DRC's lowest childhood vaccination rate usually results in high infantile morbidity and mortality rates, perpetuating health inequities. Therefore, addressing the root cause of this challenge should involve a more comprehensive approach that raises vaccine hesitancy awareness, strengthens healthcare infrastructure, and fosters partnership and collaboration among stakeholders (parents, public health authorities, healthcare providers, community, and religious leaders).

The diverse geographic areas present logistical hurdles for vaccine coverage and educational campaigns. It's also important to mention that some regions' ongoing war, conflict, and instability constitute barriers to childhood vaccine access. ([Wagner et al., 2021](#))

Therefore, a design thinking methodology, engagement with hesitant parents and public health authorities, and leveraging available resources are crucial to overcoming the low vaccination rate and improving overall children's well-being in the Congo.

Action Plan:

A design thinking approach will be employed to understand the concerns and fears of hesitant parents regarding childhood vaccination efforts in the Democratic Republic of the Congo. Identifying the underlying issues through collaborative efforts will help generate innovative ideas to solve them effectively. A prototype of potential solutions will be created and tested to ensure the feasibility and impact of increasing childhood vaccination rates in DRC. Here is the action plan to consider:

a) Empathize:

This approach involves interviews and qualitative research to engage hesitant parents and collaborate with primary care physicians and public health authorities. Interviews will focus on parents' perceptions of vaccines' effectiveness, safety, and cultural and religious beliefs. Collaborating with authorities will gather data on vaccination coverage, strategies, and challenges. Interviewing public health authorities and primary care providers will help develop long-term solutions to address hesitancy and improve vaccination rates.

b) Define:

This action plan phase analyzes collected data to identify challenges and opportunities in childhood vaccination in the DRC. It categorizes challenges into areas, communities, and regions, involving stakeholders like public health authorities, primary care providers, community leaders, religious leaders, and NGOs. The plan maps current vaccination coverage policies, infrastructure, and programs, identifying areas of improvement and gaps.

The design thinking process will require establishing clear objectives and feasibility based on research findings and stakeholder input. ([Shearer et al., 2023](#))

Objectives are: boosting vaccination acceptance, increasing rural access, engaging the community, and training primary care providers to address vaccine hesitancy, addressing empathize phase concerns.

A problem statement that reflects the concerns and challenges identified during the empathize phase should be developed and articulate the need for innovative solutions for desired outcomes.

c) Ideate:

The brainstorming phase is crucial for generating innovative ideas to address barriers and engage parents, authorities, and stakeholders. It involves workshops, collaborative sessions, design thinking, and open dialogue to develop trust. Strategies to improve vaccine acceptance include community education, campaigns, mobile vaccination units, outreach programs, and partnerships with religious leaders. ([Vaccine Hesitancy: An Evolving Public Health Threat, n.d.](#))

Innovative solutions will be developed after documenting, evaluating, and prioritizing ideas for addressing parental hesitancy using design thinking techniques like voting, clustering, and scoring.

d) Prototype:

The prototype phase aims to develop and implement pilot programs to test the practicality of addressing parent hesitancy and increasing childhood vaccination rates in low-vaccination areas. Steps include tailoring programs to specific barriers, targeting specific audiences, collaborating with healthcare providers, and implementing on a small scale. Continuous feedback is collected to analyze intervention effectiveness and identify gaps. A database is built to monitor and evaluate the impact of pilot programs, tracking vaccination rates, parental attitudes, and perceptions. Reporting data informs evidence-based decision-making for further refinement before scaling up to a larger population. ([Immunization Analysis and Insights, n.d.](#))

e) Test:

The phase aims to evaluate the impact of prototypes in addressing vaccine hesitancy and improving childhood vaccination rates in the Democratic Republic of the Congo. It involves reviewing data on parental attitudes, vaccination rates, and community perceptions, comparing pre-intervention and post-intervention vaccination rates, measuring communication strategies, educational materials, and community engagement initiatives, and analyzing feedback from parents, healthcare providers, and community leaders. Participation and collaboration between parents, authorities, and stakeholders are crucial for sustainable solutions. Continuous Evaluation, refinement, and monitoring are essential for achieving desired outcomes and improving vaccination coverage and public health.

Timeline

Here is a more comprehensive breakdown of the timetable providing details on the projected length of each step of the design thinking process based on their feasibility:

- Empathize: 2 months

The phase aims to engage parents, public health authorities, and stakeholders in the Democratic Republic of the Congo to understand the root cause of low childhood vaccination rates through qualitative research and interviews.

- Define: 1 month

Analyze previous phase data to identify challenges and opportunities in childhood vaccination in DRC, identify recurring themes, map stakeholders, establish objectives, and develop a problem statement.

- Ideate: 1 month

Address challenges by generating innovative ideas through interactive workshops, collaborative sessions, and design thinking activities. Engage community leaders, parents, professionals, and NGOs for strategy exploration and prototype selection.

- Prototype: 3 months

It involves developing pilot programs, testing effectiveness and feasibility, and adjusting interventions for small-scale interventions to increase childhood vaccination rates.

- Test: 3 months

This three-month duration will provide a comprehensive assessment of childhood vaccination rates, parental perspectives, and the effectiveness of communication strategies. Data collection, analysis, and measurement are performed during this timeframe to inform future decision-making and sustainable solutions. Ongoing reviews and adjustments will ensure adequate progress and adaptability throughout the project.

Resources

To effectively conduct the design thinking process and address the challenge of low childhood vaccination rates in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC), the following resources will be crucial:

To address the low childhood vaccination rates in the Democratic Republic of the Congo, a design thinking process requires a multidisciplinary team with experts. This involves:

-Dedicated Team Members: This team should include experts in public health, communication, community engagement, data analysis, and project management, contributing their skills and knowledge to various phases.

-Funding: Research, surveys, assessment, seminars, and pilot initiatives need enough financing. Philanthropic organizations, foreign donors, healthcare NGOs, and Congolese government institutions, including the Public Health Ministry, will provide funding.

Cost breakdown:

*Pilot Programs and Interventions: \$250,000–\$350,000 budget.

*Research and interviews: \$120,000–\$155,000 budget.

*Outreach and Communication: \$20,000–\$70,000 budget.

*Workshops and Collaborations: \$150,000–\$190,000 budget.

*Monitoring and Evaluation: \$30,000–\$80,000 budget.

- Collaboration with Stakeholders:

Stakeholders must collaborate to gather knowledge, insights, and relationships for long-term solutions.

- Access to Reliable Information: Collaboration with public health authorities and research institutions is essential for obtaining the most reliable information on childhood vaccination, its safety, benefits, and effectiveness.

- **Data Collection and Analysis Tools:** Data collection, survey instruments, and management software are essential for evidence-based decision-making and identifying effective strategies to address vaccine hesitancy.

- **Training and Capacity Building:** A design thinking process requires team building. Training programs and workshops can enhance skills in design thinking methodologies, communication strategies, data analysis, and community engagement, ensuring the team can navigate project complexities effectively.

- **Technology and Communication Channels:** to allow effective engagement and outreach of parents and communities. Social media such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, TikTok, local TV, and radio allow broader reach and targeted messaging to address concerns and barriers to vaccination.

References

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